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Smart Clothing Empowering Daily Living and Participation

Tiina Vuohijoki, Sari Merilampi & Johanna Virkki

Smart clothing applications are conventionally classified as sportswear, workwear, safety, fashion, and/or healthcare [1]. Related, but not exactly under the health category, are smart clothing items aiding participation. In other words, participatory clothing. The challenging issue in describing these participatory garments is that, as participation can be defined as “involvement in a life situation, assisted if needed” [2], the definition covers all life areas, crossing the traditional categories of smart clothing. The same garment might measure biological parameters for better awareness, provide a sense of safety, and perhaps make a fashion statement [3]. Thus, participatory clothing rarely, if at all, solely medical devices.

The mismatch between a person's functional performance and environmental requirements weakens participation and might lead to lowered well-being and quality of life. Further, a remarkable number of existing innovations in assistive technology aim to foster life engagement for those who need it the most, although they rarely fit personal needs perfectly [4]. The unfortunate reality is that it is impossible to design one participatory clothing item that fits everyone. Two complex themes come together when designing such garments, both highly personal and subjective: 1) the variation in functional performance and exact needs for assistance among people, and 2) the unpredictability of desired clothing appearance. These two factors create an impossible combination for achieving participatory clothing is that is both adjustable and customizable with mass-produced items.

“But what if we could let the users decide on all these beforementioned matters? What if the user or their relative could design, fabricate, and program the clothing, leading to one-of-a-kind items serving the individual?” asked Vuohijoki, a PhD student before starting her research.

Over the past three years, Vuohijoki has explored and experimented participatory clothing: first by defining user needs [3], then by sample fabrication with punch-needling and hand-stitching (Fig. 1) [5], [6] and finally by fabricating clothing [7], [8] aimed at enhancing user engagement, particularly for individuals facing barriers related to physical, mental, and environmental issues. Both Smart Jacket and Command Sleeve (Fig. 2) showcase the integration of technology and textile while considering the user's needs [7], [8].

The focus of her research is to reveal user ability through designing textile-based passive UHF RFID user interfaces and leaves the finishing look, purpose, and location of the interface up to the user. While the preliminary results show potential, there is still development to be done, as the tag itself is only one part of the whole system. Moreover, Vuohijoki emphasizes that the developed garments are prototypes, not purely fashion artifacts; they demonstrate the idea that can be further developed by end-users who inherently know what suits them best.

Fig. 1 Fabricated passive UHF RFID tag, inspired by initial results of [6].

Fig. 2. Command Sleeve with changeable tasks: By changing the marker, user can play music or request location via mobile phone speaker with only covering the marker attached to sleeve [8]

Acknowledgment

This article is part of the “ReACTIVE Too Journal” series aiming at showcasing the project activities, sharing case studies and technical reports by the Reliable Electronics for Tomorrow’s Active Systems ReACTIVE Too (ReACTIVE Too) project partners. The project is funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange Programme of the European Union under the Grant Agreement No 871163.

- [1] S. Jiang, O. Stange, F. O. Bätcke, S. Sultanova, and L. Sabantina, "Applications of Smart Clothing – a Brief Overview," *Communications in Development and Assembling of Textile Products*, vol. 2, no. 2, Art. no. 2, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.25367/cdatp.2021.2.p123-140.
- [2] R. J. M. Perenboom and A. M. J. Chorus, "Measuring participation according to the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF)," *Disabil Rehabil*, vol. 25, no. 11–12, pp. 577–587, Jun. 2003, doi: 10.1080/0963828031000137081.
- [3] T. Vuohijoki, T. Ihalainen, and J. Virkki, "Smart clothing and furniture for supporting participation-co-creation concepts for daily living," *SN Appl. Sci.*, vol. 5, no. 4, p. 110, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s42452-023-05315-w.
- [4] T. A. Vihriälä, R. Raisamo, T. Ihalainen, and J. Virkki, "Towards E-textiles in augmentative and alternative communication – user scenarios developed by speech and language therapists," *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, vol. 0, no. 0, pp. 1–11, 2023, doi: 10.1080/17483107.2023.2225556.
- [5] T. Vuohijoki, A. Shaikh, S. Merilampi, T. Ihalainen, and J. Virkki, "Punch-Needled Passive UHF RFID Tag Dipole Antennas – Design, Fabrication, and Initial Wireless Evaluation," in *2023 8th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech)*, Jun. 2023, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.23919/SpliTech58164.2023.10192972.
- [6] T. Vuohijoki, S. M. M. Rahman, S. Merilampi, T. Ihalainen, and J. Virkki, "Fabrication and Initial Evaluation of Hand-Stitched RFID Dipole Antennas," in *2023 IEEE 13th International Conference on RFID Technology and Applications (RFID-TA)*, Aveiro, Portugal: IEEE, Sep. 2023, pp. 162–165. doi: 10.1109/RFID-TA58140.2023.10290192.
- [7] T. Vuohijoki, T. Ihalainen, S. Merilampi, and J. Virkki, "Multidisciplinary development of Smart Jacket for elder care," *Finnish Journal of eHealth and eWelfare*, vol. 14, no. 3, Art. no. 3, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.23996/fjhw.112214.
- [8] T. Vuohijoki, S. Merilampi, T. Ihalainen, and J. Virkki, "A Prototype of an RFID-Based Command Sleeve With Changeable Microcircuits", accepted for conference publication in SpliTech 2024